

TiO₂ CLP case: a perspective on the history and how it developed

Damjana Drobne

University of Ljubljana, Biotechnical Faculty, Ljubljana; Slovenia

damjana.drobne@bf.uni-lj.si

<http://www.bionanoteam.com/>

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Content

- Starting point: TiO₂ CLP

- Report

- Conclusions and Future challenges

Introduction

EU chemical REGULATION

DG GROWTH is **EU commission service**

DG GROWTH **supervises** certain regulatory agencies; European Chemicals Agency (**ECHA**)

European Chemicals Agency (ECHA) **implements** the EU's legislation on **chemical products**

REACH, BPR and **CLP** are **EU regulations**

European Commission publishes titanium dioxide classification

On **February 18, 2020** the European Union published the delegated regulation classifying certain powder titanium dioxide (TiO₂) and powder mixtures containing TiO₂ as a **suspected carcinogen (Category 2) via inhalation** under its **EU Regulation No 1272/2008 on classification, labelling and packing (CLP)** of substances and mixtures.

<https://www.cosmeticsdesign-europe.com/Article/2020/02/19/European-Commission-publishes-titanium-dioxide-classification>

“Suspected of causing cancer through inhalation” (H351)

The regulation mandates that by **October 1, 2021 hazard labels** will be required on certain TiO₂ powder products and certain powder mixtures containing TiO₂ put on the market in the European Union.

CLH report

Proposal for Harmonised Classification and Labelling Based on Regulation (EC) 1272/2008 (CLP Regulation), Annex VI, Part 2

Substance Name: Titanium dioxide

EC Number: 236-675-5

CAS Number: 13463-67-7

Index Number: -

Contact details for dossier submitter:

ANSES (on behalf of the French MSCA)

Ministries of Consumer Affairs, Health, Labour, Ecology and Agriculture

14 rue Pierre Marie Curie

F-94701 Maisons-Alfort Cedex

reach@anses.fr

Version number: 2 Date: May 2016

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Current entry in Annex VI, CLP Regulation	None
Current proposal for consideration by RAC	Carc. 1B – H350i

France proposed a mandatory category 1B carcinogenicity classification. This would have made titanium dioxide eligible for REACH substance of very high concern (SVHC) status and inclusion on the candidate list for authorization.

<https://chemicalwatch.com/56755/rac-opinion-makes-candidate-list-unlikely-for-titanium-dioxide>

Start

In **May 2016**, The French Agency for Food, Environmental and Occupational Health & Safety (ANSES) submitted the **Harmonised Classification and Labelling (CLH) report for TiO₂** to the European Chemical Agency (ECHA).

from May 2016 to February 2020

What is TiO₂?

- Titanium dioxide, is the naturally occurring oxide of titanium with a wide range of applications, from paint to sunscreen to food coloring.

Production volumes

Global titanium dioxide market share, by application, 2018

GLOBAL TITANIUM DIOXIDE MARKET: KEY DRIVERS AND FIGURES

KEY MARKET FIGURES

PAINTS AND COATINGS

In 2016, paints and coatings dominated the global market with a share of 58%.

UVA/B FILTERS IN SUNSCREENS

It has been found that people who use sunscreen daily have 24% less skin aging.

THE MARKET IN APAC

By volume, the titanium dioxide market in APAC was 2,829.9 thousand metric tons in 2016.

GLOBAL MARKET GROWTH

2016
VALUE

6,152 metric tons

2021
VALUE

7,483.3 metric tons

1,331.3
METRIC TONS
INCREMENTAL GROWTH

technavio

Regulation of substances on the market

ECHA and the Member States developed risk-based criteria for the selection of substances for the Community rolling action plan CoRAP. Member States and ECHA will only include substances in the CoRAP **where a request for further information may help to clarify the initial concern** for that substance.

Justification for the selection of a candidate CoRAP substance Substance Name (Public Name):

Titanium dioxide

Chemical Group:

EC Number: 236-675-5

CAS Number: 13463-67-7

Submitted by: FRANCE

Published: 20/03/2013

<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> (Suspected) CMR	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Wide dispersive use	<input type="checkbox"/> Cumulative exposure
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> (Suspected) Sensitiser	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Consumer use	<input type="checkbox"/> High RCR
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> (Suspected) PBT/vPvB	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Exposure of sensitive populations	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Aggregated tonnage
<input type="checkbox"/> Suspected endocrine disruptor	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Other (provide further details below)	

TiO₂ - 1,000,000 - 10,000,000 tonnes per annum

Grounds for concern

3.5 Information to be requested to clarify the suspected risk

<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Information on toxicological properties	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Information on exposure
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Information on fate and behaviour	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Information on uses
<input type="checkbox"/> Information on ecotoxicological properties	<input type="checkbox"/> Other (provide further details below)
<input type="checkbox"/> Information on physico-chemical properties	
Exact information required to be determined during the substance evaluation	

<https://echa.europa.eu/documents/10162/a5488e9d-acb8-184c-d92b-602aad9ae43d>

Steps in TiO₂ classification

Phase I: The **Committee for Risk Assessment (RAC)** prepares the opinions for **ECHA** related to the risks of substances to human health and the environment.

Phase I: Proposal for **Harmonised Classification and Labelling**

Substance TiO₂

Phase II: Political assessment (CARACAL meetings)

The final decisions are taken by the **European Commission** (if approved, **ATP publication** follows).

Phase II: **ECHA** sends this to the European Commission, which will decide what, if any, regulatory measures should be taken.

Public consultation is one of CLP classification steps

Public consultation on TiO₂ CLP

During public consultations, **489 comments were received**, 411 of which came from various organizations: businesses, business associations and consortia from various sectors. The other comments were submitted by individuals, either in their own name or anonymously or as representatives of companies, often sharing the views of the business organizations.

Moreover, around the time of the public consultation, **27 NGOs** reacted outside the framework of the public feedback mechanism. They did not share the views of the industry.

Discussion

Topics for discussion

why has TiO₂ CLP classification provoked so much public debate and **why** is decision to classify TiO₂ as a carcinogen (Group 2B carcinogen) considered controversial?

<https://app.croneri.co.uk/feature-articles/classification-titanium-dioxide>

How MNBP-13 projects see their contribution to the topic

Contribution of Science communication

Knowledge readiness levels for risk governance (KaRL) concept

DRL 9

DRL 8

DRL 7

DRL 6

DRL 5

DRL 4

DRL 3

DRL 2

DRL 1

Human involvement

Automatization

Solution 1: Communicating and Collaborating Across Disciplines

RGF tools and approaches

Communication of science across disciplines:
Transdisciplinary approach

Examples of actionable documents / information

CLH REPORT FOR TITANIUM DIOXIDE

Dossier by MS authority

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ECHA's risk assessment committee RAC proposal with explanation

Public opinion

OPINION OF THE COMMITTEE FOR RISK ASSESSMENT ON A DOSSIER PROPOSING HARMONISED CLASSIFICATION AND LABELLING AT EU LEVEL

In accordance with Article 37 (4) of Regulation (EC) No 1272/2008, the Classification, Labelling and Packaging (CLP) Regulation, the Committee for Risk Assessment (RAC) has adopted an opinion on the proposal for harmonised classification and labelling (CLH) of:

Chemical name: Titanium dioxide

EC Number: 236-675-5

CAS Number: 13463-67-7

The proposal was submitted by France and received by RAC on 27 May 2016.

In this opinion, all classification and labelling elements are given in accordance with the CLP Regulation.

PROCESS FOR ADOPTION OF THE OPINION

France has submitted a CLH dossier containing a proposal together with the justification and background information documented in a CLH report. The CLH report was made publicly available in accordance with the requirements of the CLP Regulation at <http://echa.europa.eu/harmonised-classification-and-labelling-consultation/> on 31 May 2016. Concerned parties and Member State Competent Authorities (MSCA) were invited to submit comments and contributions by 15 July 2016.

ADOPTION OF THE OPINION OF RAC

Rapporteur, appointed by RAC: Normunds Kadikis

Co-Rapporteur, appointed by RAC: Norbert Rupprich

The opinion takes into account the comments provided by MSCAs and concerned parties in accordance with Article 37(4) of the CLP Regulation and the comments received are compiled in Annex 2.

The RAC opinion on the proposed harmonised classification and labelling was adopted on 14 September 2017 by consensus.

514 comments were received during the public consultation on the CLH report. Comments were from 5 MS, 38 individuals and the remainder from organizations.

Transdisciplinary approach

Communicating science effectively needs more than facts,
it needs **transdisciplinary approach!**

Solution 2: Communiation of science to general public

The public must be able to understand the basics of science to make informed every-day decisions.

Communicating science effectively needs more than facts!

Communication of science to general public

RGF tools and approaches

References:

Potočník, J. (2011). Commission recommendation of 18 october 2011 on the definition of nanomaterial (2011/696/EU). *Off. J. Eur. Union* 275, 38–40. Available online at: https://ec.europa.eu/research/industrial_technologies/pdf/policy/commission-recommendation-on-the-definition-of-nanomater-18102011_en.pdf.

